

Viribus unitis – utility and modeling of drug combinations

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Abstract

The opportunities that may be provided by synergistic antiviral action of drugs for battling SARS-CoV2 are currently underestimated. Modern AI technologies realized as text, data, and knowledge mining and analytics tools provide the researchers with unprecedented opportunities for “smart” design of drug combinations with synergistic antiviral activities. The goal of this talk is to emphasize combination therapy as a potential treatment against COVID-19 and to utilize the combination of modern machine learning and AI technologies with our expertise to select the most promising drug combinations with further experimental validation. We hypothesized that combining drugs with independent mechanisms of action could result in synergy against SARS-CoV-2, thus generating better antiviral efficacy. Using *in silico* approaches, we prioritized 73 combinations of 32 drugs with potential activity against SARS-CoV-2 and then tested them *in vitro*. Sixteen synergistic and eight antagonistic combinations were identified; among 16 synergistic cases, combinations of the FDA-approved drug nitazoxanide with remdesivir, amodiaquine, or umifenovir were most notable, all exhibiting significant synergy against SARS-CoV-2 in a cell model. However, the combination of remdesivir and lysosomotropic drugs, such as hydroxychloroquine, demonstrated strong antagonism. Overall, these results highlight the utility of drug repurposing and preclinical testing of drug combinations for discovering potential therapies to treat COVID-19.